

1 **The Dynamics of Megafire Smoke Plumes in Climate**
2 **Models: Why a Converged Solution Matters for**
3 **Physical Interpretations**

4 **S.R. Guimond¹, J. Reisner², and M. Dubey²**

5 ¹Joint Center for Earth Systems Technology and Department of Physics, University of Maryland

6 Baltimore County, Baltimore, MD, USA

7 ²Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM, USA

8 **Key Points:**

- 9 • Simulations of megafire smoke plumes require fully resolved dynamics ($\sim 8 \Delta x$)
10 in order to accurately characterize plume properties (e.g., black carbon fraction)
11 • For the 2017 British Columbia event, smoke injected at ~ 12 km height requires
12 a reduction in black carbon fraction by 50% to match observations for external
13 mixtures
14 • Analysis of the vorticity dynamics shows that smoke plume anti-cyclonic vortices
15 form (decay) due to the dilution (concentration) of cyclonic absolute vorticity

Corresponding author: Stephen R. Guimond, sguimond@umbc.edu

Abstract

As the climate system warms, megafires have become more frequent with devastating effects. A byproduct of these events is the creation of smoke plumes that can rise into the stratosphere and spread across the globe where they reside for many months. To gain a deeper understanding of the plume dynamics, global climate simulations of a megafire were performed at a wide range of grid spacings from 2.0° down to 7 km, including a 7 km nonhydrostatic experiment. The analysis focuses on how the resolved dynamics affects the specification of the plume characteristics such as injection height and black carbon (BC) mass. Prior studies initialize the smoke plume at one or a few grid points and this is shown here to produce severely dissipative dynamics. In order to validate such simulations with observations, enhancements of the plume characteristics to offset the dissipation is necessary. Using a numerically converged simulation, sensitivity tests show that to approximate the observed stratospheric lifetime, a reduction in BC fraction by 50% is necessary for external mixtures. The vorticity dynamics of the plume is also analyzed with a Lagrangian budget to understand the mechanisms responsible for the evolution of a collocated anticyclonic vortex. The results can be distilled down into a simple conceptual model. As the plume rises, the air diverges at the top of the updraft where the largest concentrations of smoke are found. This divergence induces a dilution of the background cyclonic absolute vorticity producing an anticyclonic vortex. Vortex decay occurs from opposite arguments.

Plain Language Summary

Recently, there has been an increase in large and intense wildfires (“megafires”) across the Earth in response to global warming. These megafire events produce large amounts of smoke that can rise high up in the atmosphere to a level well above clouds and weather. The smoke can stay at these high levels for long periods of time and spread across much of the Earth, which blocks sunlight from reaching the surface. It is important to understand the properties of these smoke plumes and how to correctly predict their consequences on human life. However, uncertainties in both observations and models make it difficult to achieve these goals. In particular, models contain various sources of uncertainty that can interact in complex ways. In this paper, we show that previous research has used a model grid spacing that does not sample the plume accurately, which leads to errors that affect the interpretation of the smoke properties, evolution of the plume and potential climatic effects. By choosing a model grid spacing that accurately samples the plume structure, the errors in the dynamics component of the model can be minimized, providing a baseline for reducing uncertainty in other parts of the system.

1 Introduction

In the last several years, there has been a dramatic increase in large, intense wildfires (“megafires”) in various regions of the world that have burned millions of acres of forests, destroyed homes and businesses and resulted in substantial deaths (e.g., Jolly et al., 2015; Wikipedia contributors, 2022). The production of smoke from these fires can be rapidly transported deep into the stratosphere through a combination of pyrocumulonimbus (pyroCb) events and radiation-driven lift, where it can spread globally and reside for many months to years (e.g., Fromm et al., 2005; Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018). Recent megafires in British Columbia (2017; BC17) and Australia (2019/2020) have produced stratospheric aerosol mass burdens between $\sim 0.2 - 1.0$ Tg, which is equivalent to that from a moderate volcanic eruption (Peterson et al., 2021).

A natural question to ask is: what are the impacts of these stratospheric smoke plumes on climate? While some studies have estimated the radiative forcing resulting from megafires, the global mean of this forcing is usually small and sometimes of opposite sign (Christian

et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021), casting doubt on their effects on the climate system. Christian et al. (2019) studied the BC17 megafire event and estimated a direct top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) radiative forcing between $+0.01$ and $+0.02 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ compared to values between -0.7 and -1.3 Wm^{-2} from the 2008 Kasatochi volcano eruption (Wang et al., 2013). However, Christian et al. (2019) did not employ a coupled climate model in their radiative forcing calculations, eliminating aerosol indirect effects, which could result in significant uncertainty. Das et al. (2021) performed coupled climate model simulations of the BC17 event and found TOA forcing of $-0.03 \pm 0.01 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$. While the BC17 forcings are small and potentially within the noise, for larger megafires, such as the 2019/2020 Australian event, the radiative effects can be significant with TOA forcing values of $-0.31 \pm 0.09 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ (Khaykin et al., 2020) and mean surface temperature cooling of up to -0.2 K (D'Angelo et al., 2022).

It is clear that more in-depth studies are needed to understand the potential regional and global effects of megafire smoke plumes. To provide a more comprehensive analysis of potential climatic effects, it is important to understand the mechanisms controlling the transport of smoke and to quantify characteristics of the smoke plumes such as total mass, breakdown of that mass into organic aerosol (the focus here is on organic carbon or OC) and black carbon (BC) fractions, mean particle radius, peak height and stratospheric residence time, among others. Several recent studies have analyzed specific megafire cases to achieve this understanding and they typically utilize either satellite observations alone or in combination with climate models. The focus of the present paper is on the plume and vorticity dynamics of the BC17 megafire and therefore, a brief description of this event is discussed next. However, the discussion, results and conclusions of the present paper are sufficiently general such that they are relevant to a broader scope of megafire events.

The BC17 megafire was initiated on August 12, 2017 and produced a series of five discrete pyroCbs that lasted for about a 5 h period. Lidar satellite observations indicated that smoke from the pyroCbs reached altitudes of up to $\sim 13 \text{ km}$ about 8 h after the 5 h pulsing period at 1045 UTC 13 August, which is $\sim 1 \text{ km}$ above the local tropopause of $\sim 12 \text{ km}$ (Peterson et al., 2018). The smoke is thought to have been directly injected into the stratosphere by the pyroCbs, but there are uncertainties with this interpretation. About 33 h later at 1930 UTC 14 August, lidar observations clearly show significant smoke at heights of $\sim 13.5 \text{ km}$, illustrating the important role of radiative lofting effects (Torres et al., 2020). The peak height of the smoke plume was $\sim 22 \text{ km}$ about three weeks after the fire initiation with elevated lidar backscatter detected for ~ 4 months or more (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018). In addition, the ascent rate of the BC17 plume in the first few days was estimated at $\sim 2 - 3 \text{ km/day}$ and over a three week time period averaged $\sim 0.5 \text{ km/day}$ (Khaykin et al., 2018).

Initially, the smoke is confined to the cores of the pyroCbs, which have a scale on the order of 10 km . However, as the pyroCbs merge and penetrate the tropopause, their outflow coupled with the strong winds near the tropopause can spread the smoke to a large horizontal area, on the order of many thousands of square kilometers. Peterson et al. (2018) estimated a smoke area of $\sim 800,000 \text{ km}^2$ based on an aerosol index from satellite observations, but the area of dense smoke is much smaller than this value. Estimates of the total smoke mass produced by the BC17 megafire ($0.1 - 0.3 \text{ Tg}$) were calculated using two methods. The first method integrates the particle mass density over the volume of smoke contained in the stratosphere using lidar data, while the second method uses observations of the total burned area, fuel consumption and smoke emissions. While reasonable estimates can be obtained, there is significant uncertainty ($\sim 50\%$) in the mean mass value of 0.2 Tg .

The breakdown of smoke emissions from megafires into BC and OC is critical for plume lofting effects because BC is a strong absorber of radiation across the solar spectrum, while OC, which dominates the total smoke mass, is a very weak absorber. The

118 associated heating of the plume from these radiative effects can loft the smoke high into
 119 the stratosphere (Malone et al., 1985). Unfortunately, there is also significant uncertainty
 120 in the BC fraction in the range of $\sim 2 - 6\%$ as described below. In addition, the micro-
 121 physical aspects of smoke particle evolution are highly uncertain and they are treated
 122 simply in climate models. The microphysical aspects include mixing processes with other
 123 aerosols and phases of water as well as interactions with radiation (optical properties),
 124 which are complex, variable and difficult to measure.

125 Yu et al. (2019) used the Community Earth System Model (CESM) at $1.9^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$
 126 horizontal resolution and 56 vertical levels (~ 1 km resolution near the tropopause) to
 127 determine the BC content and stratospheric residence time of the BC17 smoke plume.
 128 This was done by perturbing the BC fraction over a range of values (1 - 5 %) and com-
 129 paring the peak height of the simulated plume to satellite observations. The plume was
 130 initialized at 12 - 13 km height, seemingly at one grid point near the fire epicenter, with
 131 0.3 Tg of total mass. With this setup, Yu et al. (2019) inferred that a 2 % BC fraction
 132 best matched observations. They estimated a ~ 5 month stratospheric residence time
 133 (e-folding time) from observations and an ~ 8 month e-folding time from the simulations
 134 with 2% BC fraction. The authors determined that in order to match the observed e-
 135 folding time, a photochemical loss of OC must be invoked.

136 Torres et al. (2020) used the NASA Goddard Earth Observing System (GEOS) global
 137 climate model at ~ 55 km ($\sim 0.5^\circ$) horizontal resolution and 72 vertical levels (also \sim
 138 1 km resolution near the tropopause) to study the BC17 event. The authors used a to-
 139 tal smoke mass of 0.3 Tg and assumed a BC fraction of 2.5%. Independent estimates of
 140 the total smoke mass were computed and they found a range of 0.18 - 0.35 Tg, similar
 141 to Peterson et al. (2018). The smoke mass was spread evenly across a $2^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ area in
 142 the horizontal (4 - 5 grid points covering the plume) and injected uniformly between 10
 143 - 12 km altitude, which is just below the tropopause height. The main takeaway from
 144 this study is the significant impact of radiative self-lofting in driving the plume into the
 145 stratosphere to high altitudes (up to 20 - 22 km height) with diabatic heating rates of
 146 20 K/day or more.

147 Das et al. (2021) used the simulation described in Torres et al. (2020) to study ad-
 148 ditional aspects of the BC17 event, including the radiative forcing discussed above. They
 149 found a stratospheric e-folding time of 140 days (4.67 months) from their simulation af-
 150 ter starting the calculation 38 days from the initial injection. An estimate of this time-
 151 scale from a satellite retrieval was similar (5 months) although the decay rate appears
 152 slightly steeper than the model. Both Christian et al. (2019) and Das et al. (2021) do
 153 not need to include a photochemical loss of OC to approach the observed stratospheric
 154 e-folding time, casting doubt on the results presented in Yu et al. (2019).

155 D'Angelo et al. (2022) (hereafter D22) conducted global simulations of the BC17
 156 event from the CESM and GEOS models to understand the sensitivity of plume peak
 157 height and stratospheric residence time to BC fraction (2 - 6 %), injection height (12 -
 158 14 km), total mass (0.1 - 0.3 Tg) and particle radius (200 - 350 nm). The control sim-
 159 ulations used a BC fraction of 2%, stratospheric injection height of ~ 13.5 km and mean
 160 particle radius of 300 - 350 nm. The total injected mass was 0.4 Tg, but only 0.2 Tg was
 161 injected at ~ 13.5 km height with the other 0.2 Tg spread evenly below this altitude.
 162 This setup mirrors that of Christian et al. (2019). The control setup produced a strato-
 163 spheric e-folding time of ~ 5 months for the CESM model and ~ 6 months for the GEOS
 164 model.

165 D22 found the most sensitive parameters (in order from largest to smallest) to be
 166 plume injection height, total mass/BC fraction (together determine BC load) and par-
 167 ticle radius. These parameters are not only sensitive in models, but they have signifi-
 168 cant uncertainty from measurements as described above. The particle sizes, however, have
 169 minimal sensitivity for a reasonable measurement range. The plume injection height is

170 a consequence of the typically very coarse resolution of climate models, which cannot re-
 171 solve the natural life cycle of pyroCbs in any form. As a result, the altitude that con-
 172 vection transports smoke into the upper atmosphere must be specified to initialize the
 173 model. For the BC17 case, measurements of this altitude are uncertain with values rang-
 174 ing from $\sim 11 - 14$ km.

175 There is another source of uncertainty that has not been addressed methodically
 176 with megafire studies: the effects of resolved energetics in the climate models and feed-
 177 backs to the uncertainties associated with the plume characteristics. Most of the mod-
 178 eling studies are conducted with very coarse grid spacing (e.g., $1^\circ - 2^\circ$) with the plume
 179 initialized at one grid point, although Torres et al. (2020) and Das et al. (2021) used 0.5°
 180 covering the plume with 4 - 5 grid points. What are the effects of higher resolution on
 181 the smoke plume dynamics (e.g., transport, large-scale mixing and interactions with clouds)
 182 and interplay with the specified plume characteristics (e.g., injection height, total smoke
 183 mass and BC fraction)? The purpose of this paper is to answer these questions and make
 184 recommendations to the community for a minimally resolvable modeling system that can
 185 narrow the uncertainty gap for the megafire problem.

186 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, a description of
 187 the numerical model and setup of the simulations is presented. Simulations are conducted
 188 at a wide range of resolutions to study the effects of resolved dynamics: 2.0° , 1.0° , 0.25° ,
 189 7 km and 7 km-nonhydrostatic. Analysis of the characteristics and transport of the sim-
 190 ulated smoke plumes is described in Section 3. Section 3 also presents an analysis of the
 191 kinetic energy spectra of the simulations and discusses the effective resolution of the GEOS
 192 modeling system. Section 4 presents an analysis of the vorticity dynamics of the plumes
 193 and how this relates to the plume lifetime. Important implications of this work for the
 194 megafire problem are given in Section 5. Future work is also discussed in this section.

195 **2 Numerical Simulations**

196 **2.1 Description and setup of climate model**

197 To examine the global effects of localized megafire smoke plumes, numerical sim-
 198 ulations of the BC17 event were conducted with the atmospheric component of the NASA
 199 GEOS climate model. The NASA GEOS is a finite volume general circulation model that
 200 solves the hydrostatic or nonhydrostatic equations of motion on a cubed sphere grid with
 201 a Lagrangian vertical coordinate (Lin, 2004). The dynamic core is coupled to various phys-
 202 ical models for moist processes, radiation, turbulence, gravity wave drag, etc. (Molod
 203 et al., 2015) and is initialized with reanalysis data that incorporates various observations
 204 (MERRA-2) (Rienecker et al., 2008). In this study, the Goddard Chemistry, Aerosol, Ra-
 205 diation and Transport (GOCART) (Chin et al., 2002) model is utilized to represent smoke
 206 plumes with a focus on the bins for BC and OC aerosol. The aerosols in GOCART are
 207 treated as an external mixture and are fully coupled to the dynamic core and radiation
 208 packages. The source of BC/OC for the BC17 event is described below and the sinks in-
 209 clude wet scavenging and dry deposition. Given the focus on the stratosphere, the dry
 210 deposition processes are most important. This dry deposition is a parameterization of
 211 gravitational settling based on particle size and air viscosity (Chin et al., 2002). Also note
 212 that no interactive chemistry model is employed in the simulations. These simplifications
 213 reduce the degrees of freedom in the simulations and places the focus of the analysis on
 214 the dynamics of the problem.

215 Simulations with GEOS are conducted with a wide range of uniform horizontal grid
 216 spacings across the globe: 2.0° , 1.0° , 0.25° and 7 km. The vertical grid for all simulations
 217 was set to 72 hybrid sigma-pressure vertical layers from the surface to the model top at
 218 0.01 hPa. Utilization of the same vertical grid for all simulations enables a direct com-
 219 parison of the resolved energetics of each simulation. The vertical grid spacing is ~ 1 km

220 where the smoke plume is initialized in the stratosphere. These simulations are all run
 221 with hydrostatic dynamics, but an additional run at 7 km is conducted with nonhydro-
 222 static dynamics to examine the effects of the vertical inertial terms (advection of ver-
 223 tical velocity plus the local time tendency), as well as a diffusion term, on the plume heights
 224 and stratospheric residence time of the smoke. In general, nonhydrostatic effects become
 225 more important for scales of ~ 10 km and below (e.g., Weisman et al., 1997). Also, note
 226 that the GEOS model is run in a “free” mode without observational nudging and in this
 227 sense represents a true predictive simulation. The MERRA-2 reanalysis fields are used
 228 as initial conditions for the simulations and the model is started at 2100 UTC 9 August
 229 2017, which is about three days prior to the injection of smoke. This allows the model
 230 to spin-up for a period of time and develop a more robust energy spectrum.

231 The BC17 plume is represented in the model by injecting smoke mass following the
 232 specification outlined in Christian et al. (2019) and D22 due to the simplicity and abil-
 233 ity to compare with prior work. For the 2.0° simulation, the smoke mass is initialized
 234 at a single grid point (close to $53.5^\circ\text{N}, 123.0^\circ\text{W}$; an approximate epicenter for the BC17
 235 plume) with 0.2 Tg injected at ~ 13.5 km height in the stratosphere and 0.2 Tg spread
 236 evenly in the troposphere. Of the total mass, 98% is specified as OC and 2% as BC fol-
 237 lowing the results of Yu et al. (2019) and D22. This smoke profile is held fixed in the model
 238 for a 5 h time period starting at 1900 UTC 12 August 2017. A mean particle radius of
 239 350 nm is used for all simulations. Similarities and differences of the smoke plume ini-
 240 tialization described here with that from prior work can be found in the introduction sec-
 241 tion.

242 The setup of the simulations at the other grid spacings is identical to that described
 243 above except the smoke mass is spread evenly across the higher resolution grids to match
 244 the 2.0° grid cell area. For example, the smoke mass is spread evenly across 4 grid points
 245 (2 in each horizontal dimension) for the 1.0° simulation, 64 grid points for the 0.25° and
 246 1024 grid points for the 7 km runs in the same location as the 2.0° cell. Integration of
 247 the total smoke mass on the native cubed sphere grid showed nearly identical values across
 248 all simulations indicating a consistent set of initial forcing with uniform smoke concen-
 249 tration. For post-processing, all model output is interpolated to a regularly spaced lat-
 250 itude/longitude grid that matches the listed simulation resolution.

251 **3 Characteristics of Plume Evolution**

252 **3.1 Stratospheric Lifetime and Smoke Structure**

253 To summarize the smoke plume evolution in the simulations, a time series of the
 254 globally integrated stratospheric smoke burden at a wide range of horizontal grid spac-
 255 ings is presented in Fig. 1. In this analysis, the stratosphere is loosely defined as heights
 256 above 150 hPa or ~ 12.5 km in the region where the plume is present. All simulations
 257 are run up until the plume stratospheric lifetime, which is defined as where the peak strato-
 258 spheric mass (sampled at ~ 6 days into the simulations) falls off to $1/e$, using the glob-
 259 ally integrated values shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1 and all other figures shown in this pa-
 260 per, time refers to the number of days after the start of the plume forcing (1900 UTC
 261 12 August 2017).

262 Figure 1 shows that the 2.0° simulation falls off very rapidly with a lifetime of 3.5
 263 months, followed by the 1.0° simulation at 5.9 months, 7 km nonhydrostatic at 6.8 months,
 264 7 km at 6.9 months and 0.25° at 7.2 months. Using the 7 km simulation as the high res-
 265 olution reference to evaluate the other hydrostatic runs, the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations sig-
 266 nificantly underestimate the stratospheric lifetime by $\sim 50\%$ and 15% , respectively, while
 267 the 0.25° simulation only slightly overestimates the lifetime by $\sim 4\%$. The 7 km nonhy-
 268 drostatic lifetime is slightly less than the corresponding 7 km hydrostatic value, which
 269 indicates that nonhydrostatic dynamics (including the vertical inertial term as well as

Figure 1: Time series of the globally integrated stratospheric (above 150 hPa) smoke burden in Tg for simulations at a wide range of horizontal grid spacings.

270 a diffusion term) are contributing an overall dissipative effect on the plume lofting and
 271 stratospheric lifetime. Even finer grid spacing than 7 km will likely lead to additional
 272 small differences, but such simulations are an enormous computational burden and are
 273 left for future work.

274 Figure 1 also shows there is some variability in the individual curves, with the ex-
 275 ception of the 2.0° simulation, at time periods less than about 30 - 50 days due to vari-
 276 ability in the horizontal and vertical transport of the smoke. After about 50 days, the
 277 curves become smooth, which is consistent with the slow and steady removal of smoke
 278 from the stratosphere by sedimentation. It is difficult to estimate the stratospheric life-
 279 time from observations due to smoke plume detection issues (limited sampling in space
 280 and time, signal-to-noise ratio of instrument, etc), but studies have indicated that ~ 5
 281 months is a reasonable value (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019;
 282 Das et al., 2021). However, in this section, we are not as concerned with the absolute
 283 truth of the simulations, which are only quasi-realistic representations of the BC17 event.
 284 For example, there are various unknown and uncertain factors surrounding the plume
 285 characteristics as described in the introduction. Instead, we are focused on studying the
 286 relative truth of the simulations and the reasons for the wide range of variability pre-
 287 sented in Fig. 1 that can guide more focused case studies of the BC17 event or other megafire
 288 cases.

289 The stratospheric lifetime discussed above is directly related to the peak height the
 290 plume reaches in each simulation. Figure 2 shows the zonal mean smoke mixing ratio

Figure 2: Zonal mean total smoke mixing ratio in kg/kg at 6.2 days into the simulations for varying resolutions, (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km. The red line shows the tropopause height.

291 as a function of latitude and height at 6.2 days into the simulations. The peak height
 292 of the plume, defined qualitatively as the leading edge of the large smoke mixing ratio
 293 core, varies widely with resolution. The peak height values are ~ 18 km, 23 km, 32 km
 294 and 30 km in the 2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25° and 7 km simulations, respectively. Relative to the 7
 295 km reference simulation, the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations drastically underestimate the peak
 296 height by 40% and 23%, respectively, while the 0.25° simulation slightly overestimates
 297 the peak height by about 6%. The 2.0° and 1.0° simulations have one primary smoke core
 298 that is concentrated near 60° latitude, while the 0.25° and 7 km simulations have two
 299 cores with one near 60° latitude and the other closer to 70° latitude. The two smoke cores
 300 are more distinct in the 7 km simulation. The vast majority of the smoke is above the
 301 tropopause at this time in all simulations, but the dense smoke is closer to this bound-
 302 ary in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations.

303 At 16.2 days into the simulations, shown in Fig. 3, the peak height of the plumes
 304 are ~ 19 km, 30 km, 38 km and 35 km in the 2.0°, 1.0°, 0.25° and 7 km simulations, re-
 305 spectively. The 2.0° and 1.0° simulations underestimate the peak height by $\sim 46\%$ and
 306 14%, respectively, while the 0.25° simulation slightly overestimates this height by $\sim 8\%$.
 307 The rise rate of the 1.0° simulation is largest at 0.7 km/day, followed by the 0.25° (0.6
 308 km/day), 7 km (0.5 km/day) and 2.0° (0.1 km/day). Most of the plumes are concentrated
 309 into one column with the exception of the 7 km run, which continues to display two main

Figure 3: The same as in Fig. 2, only at 16.2 days.

310 cores with one centered at $\sim 45^\circ$ latitude and 23 km height and the other at $\sim 80^\circ$ lat-
 311 itude and 26 km height. Nearly all the smoke is above the tropopause at this time pe-
 312 riod, but the 2.0° simulation (Fig. 3a) shows large concentrations sitting very close to
 313 the edge of the boundary. Note that the peak height of the plumes over time are found
 314 at $\sim 20 - 25$ days into the simulations with values not much larger than that described
 315 here at 16.2 days.

316 The vertical transport of the plumes observed in Figs. 2 and 3 is due to the self-
 317 lofting effect described in the introduction whereby BC absorbs solar radiation and forms
 318 a heating anomaly, which causes a buoyant updraft. The large variability in the solu-
 319 tions with grid spacing, which all have the same plume initialization and model setup,
 320 is due to the effects of resolved energetics in the model. Detailed examination of this ef-
 321 fect will be presented in section 3.2.

322 Figure 4 shows the horizontal structure of the smoke plume at 6.2 days by verti-
 323 cally integrating the total smoke mixing ratio over the entire model atmosphere. At this
 324 time period, the 2.0° run (Fig. 4a) shows a single ball of smoke located over the Hud-
 325 son Bay in Canada with a long tail of elevated concentrations extending across the At-
 326 lantic Ocean and into Western Europe. The other resolution simulations have similar
 327 placement of the large-scale features, but the single ball of smoke in the 2.0° run is broken
 328 down into increasingly smaller-scale structures that move smoke further outward from
 329 the core region. For example, in the 1.0° (Fig. 4b), 0.25° (Fig. 4c) and 7 km (Fig. 4d)

Figure 4: Vertically integrated total smoke mixing ratio in kg/Tg over the entire model atmosphere at 6.2 days into the simulations for varying resolutions, (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km.

Figure 5: The same as in Fig. 4, only at 16.2 days.

330 simulations, high concentrations of smoke are found in the Southeastern United States
 331 and in the 0.25° and 7 km runs more smoke has moved North and West into far North-
 332 ern Canada near the Beaufort Sea. The main location of the smoke plume over North-
 333 eastern Canada (near Hudson Bay) depicted in the modeling results are in general agree-
 334 ment with satellite observations close to this time period (~ 19 August, 2017) (Khaykin
 335 et al., 2018).

336 At 16.2 days (Fig. 5), the horizontal structure of the smoke plume is significantly
 337 different between the various resolution simulations. In the 2.0° run (Fig. 5a) the high-
 338 est smoke concentrations are no longer organized into a coherent, circular structure but
 339 instead are stretched and diffused over the Greenland region. The other resolution sim-

340 ulations display a concentrated, circular structure with peak smoke mixing ratio values
 341 at the center. In the 1.0° run (Fig. 5b) this structure is located over Eastern Canada while
 342 in the 0.25° run (Fig. 5c) the ball of smoke is centered just off of Greenland. In the 7 km
 343 run (Fig. 5d), two circular regions of smoke exist with the larger feature located over the
 344 Northern Great Plains of the United States and the smaller feature located just to the
 345 West of Greenland. Lower values of smoke mixing ratio are scattered North of 30° N lat-
 346 itude in roughly similar locations in all simulations.

347 Satellite observations close to this time period (~ 29 August, 2017) (Khaykin et
 348 al., 2018) indicate that the smoke plume has encircled the globe and is located back near
 349 Western Canada, which is in closer agreement with the 7 km resolution simulation. How-
 350 ever, at this stage of the paper, we are only establishing relative truth between the simu-
 351 lations and their variability, with the 7 km hydrostatic run serving as the high resolu-
 352 tion reference. The horizontal structure differences between the various resolution simu-
 353 lations at this time is due to the differing heights of the plumes and associated wind
 354 fields that drive the transport at those heights as well as the nonlinear evolution. The
 355 nonlinear evolution is dependent on the resolved energetics of each simulation and will
 356 cause greater divergence among the simulation members as time moves forward. This
 357 is partly why the smoke horizontal structure at 6.2 days is in much better agreement than
 358 that shown at 16.2 days.

359 3.2 Kinetic Energy Spectra

360 The previous section demonstrated large variability in the stratospheric lifetime
 361 and smoke structure as a function of model grid spacing for the exact same parameters
 362 defining the initialized smoke plume. The main source of this variability is the resolved
 363 energetics of the GEOS modeling system and the associated sampling of the initialized
 364 smoke plume. To demonstrate this point, spectral analysis of the model data is performed.

365 The discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of a variable Ψ in one spatial dimension λ
 366 on a periodic domain with constant grid spacing can be written

$$367 \Psi(\lambda_n) = \sum_{m=-Q}^Q F(k_m) e^{ik_m \lambda_n} = F(0) + 2 \left| \sum_{m=1}^Q F(k_m) e^{ik_m \lambda_n} \right| \quad (1)$$

368 where $\lambda_n = L(n-1)/N$ is the position along the λ dimension for index n over domain
 369 length L with N grid points, $k_m = 2\pi m/L$ is the wavenumber for index m , and Q rep-
 370 represents the highest wavenumber index on the grid (length scale of two times the grid spac-
 371 ing). The complex Fourier coefficients are given by

$$372 F(k_m) = N^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^N \Psi(\lambda_n) e^{-ik_m \lambda_n}. \quad (2)$$

373 In the calculation of the DFT, it is common practice to report on the positive wavenum-
 374 bers only, which requires multiplying wavenumbers larger than zero by a factor of two
 375 to account for the removal of the negative side of the spectrum. For each model simu-
 376 lation, the DFT is computed for each horizontal velocity component along the λ direc-
 377 tion (latitude) according to the equations above and the kinetic energy spectrum per unit
 378 mass is calculated,

$$379 E(k) = \frac{\hat{u}^2 + \hat{v}^2}{2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Horizontal kinetic energy spectra (m^2/s^2) averaged over the $40^\circ - 70^\circ N$ latitude band and $150 - 10 hPa$ in height at various resolutions in GEOS for (a) 1.2 days, (b) 6.2 days, (c) 11.2 days and (d) 16.2 days into the simulations. The dashed black and purple lines denote the -3 and $-5/3$ spectral slopes of large-scale and mesoscale kinetic energy, respectively, from theory and observations. The “P” letter marks the scale of the initial smoke plume forcing.

380 where the hat over the velocity variables denotes the DFT field. The kinetic energy spec-
 381 trum is then averaged over the $40^\circ N - 70^\circ N$ latitudinal band and the $150 - 10 hPa$ layer
 382 where the smoke plume activity is largest.

383 Figure 6 shows the mean horizontal kinetic energy spectra for the various resolu-
 384 tion simulations at early time periods ($t \leq \sim 16$ days) in the simulations when much of
 385 the lofting dynamics takes place. At all time periods shown in Fig. 6, the kinetic energy
 386 is significantly damped in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations (especially the 2.0° run)
 387 relative to the 0.25° and $7 km$ simulations (especially the 2.0° run) from scales of $\sim 200 km - 1000 km$. Most of the plume
 388 dynamics is occurring within this wavelength band given that the scale of the initial dis-
 389 turbance is $\sim 500 km$ (marked in Fig. 6), which is near the minimum resolvable wave-
 390 length of the 2.0° simulation ($2 \Delta x$, where Δx is the approximate grid spacing of the sim-
 391 ulations). The 0.25° simulation spectra are very similar to the $7 km$ simulation spectra
 392 in the $\sim 200 km - 1000 km$ wavelength band, which indicates that the 0.25° simulation
 393 is nearly converged for the majority of the plume dynamics. This result is consistent with
 394 the statistics presented in section 3.1, where the 0.25° run produced small errors rela-
 395 tive to the $7 km$ reference simulation. Furthermore, Fig. 6 illustrates that only the 0.25°
 396 and $7 km$ simulations match the slopes of kinetic energy from theory and observations
 397 (e.g., Nastrom & Gage, 1985). In the $\sim 200 km - 1000 km$ wavelength band, the 0.25°

398 and 7 km simulations tend to follow a -3 spectral slope (“large scales”) at 1.2 and 6.2
 399 days (Figs. 6a and b, respectively), but evolve a bit closer to a -5/3 slope (“mesoscales”)
 400 at 11.2 and 16.2 days (Figs. 6c and d, respectively). This shift is subtle and not overly
 401 significant given that there is an overlap in the observed spectral slopes in this wavelength
 402 band.

403 Figure 6 also shows the 0.25° simulation has damped kinetic energy relative to the
 404 7 km run from scales of ~ 50 km - 300 km, including some subtle temporal variability
 405 in the spectra. The wavelength where the 0.25° run begins to dissipate kinetic energy
 406 relative to the 7 km run narrows from ~ 300 km wavelength (Figs. 6a,b,c) down to \sim
 407 200 km wavelength (Fig. 6d). These results indicate that the effective resolution of the
 408 GEOS modeling system is $\sim 7 - 8 \Delta x$, which is similar to other global modeling systems
 409 (e.g., Skamarock et al., 2014). *Thus, in order to produce a dynamically accurate and well-*
 410 *resolved simulation, the smoke plume must be sampled by the model grid with ~ 8 grid*
 411 *points, which should produce the correct slope of kinetic energy as demonstrated in Fig. 6.*

412 3.3 Optimal Simulations

413 The previous sub-section illustrated that in order to ensure a dynamically accu-
 414 rate evolution, the plume must be sampled by the model grid at $\sim 7 - 8 \Delta x$, which re-
 415 sults in 0.25° spacing for the initial conditions specified in this work. Given this setting
 416 for the dynamics, how should the other uncertain parameters defining the smoke plume
 417 (injection height, total smoke mass, BC fraction and particle radius) be specified to pro-
 418 duce an optimal simulation?

419 Several sensitivity tests were conducted with 0.25° spacing to examine the optimal
 420 settings of these parameters relative to observations. The observations used to constrain
 421 this exercise are estimates of the stratospheric lifetime of the smoke plume (~ 5 months)
 422 (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021) and to some
 423 extent peak heights (~ 22 km) (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Das et al.,
 424 2021).

425 The injection height used in the initial simulations (13.5 km) was determined to
 426 be too high based on observational estimates that placed the plumes at 11.5 - 12.5 km
 427 height with the best estimate likely at or slightly above the local tropopause height (\sim
 428 12 km) (Peterson et al., 2018). This injection height is also utilized in previous model-
 429 ing studies (e.g., Yu et al., 2019). For the sensitivity tests discussed here, simulations
 430 were performed with an injection height of 11.5 km and 12.5 km, given the vertical grid
 431 spacing of the chosen model grid (1.0 km). The total column smoke mass (0.4 Tg with
 432 0.2 Tg injected in the stratosphere) and particle radius (350 nm) were not changed. Some
 433 short (60 day) sensitivity tests that examined the impact of the 0.2 Tg of smoke spread
 434 evenly throughout the troposphere were also conducted. These tests showed that by re-
 435 moving the 0.2 Tg of smoke in the troposphere, the total smoke mass in the stratosphere
 436 is reduced by only $\sim 4\%$. This indicates that for the distribution of mass utilized here,
 437 the amount of smoke rising into the stratosphere from the troposphere is quite small. Thus,
 438 our focus is on the smoke injected in the stratosphere. For the 11.5 km injection height
 439 a BC mass fraction of 2% was utilized, as in the initial set of simulations, while for the
 440 12.5 km height, BC mass fractions of 0.5%, 0.75% and 2% were performed. Table 1 sum-
 441 marizes the smoke plume and model resolution settings utilized for these sensitivity tests
 442 along with those for the control experiments.

443 Figure 7 shows the results of some of these 0.25° sensitivity tests in terms of the
 444 horizontally averaged total smoke mixing ratio. The center of mass of the smoke plume
 445 is drawn on each simulation as a measure of the plume height. It should be noted that
 446 there are uncertainties comparing this height to observations, such as from lidar, due to
 447 the difficulties in simulating the penetration depth of the instrument signal into the smoke

Figure 7: Horizontally averaged total smoke mixing ratio (kg/Tg) as a function of time and height for 0.25° grid spacing simulations with (a) 11.5 km injection height and 2.0% BC fraction, denoted "Perturb1" in Table 1, (b) 12.5 km injection height and 2.0% BC fraction, denoted "Perturb2" in Table 1 and (c) 12.5 km injection height and 0.75% BC fraction, one of the tests labeled "Perturb3" in Table 1. The black line in each figure denotes the center of mass of the smoke plume.

448 as well as other instrument effects. Nevertheless, the height metric from the simulations
 449 assists in tuning the simulations to observations.

450 Figure 7a shows results for an injection height of 11.5 km with 2.0% BC fraction,
 451 which produced a 4.4 month e-decay timescale, a bit too short relative to observations.
 452 It appears the height of the plume is too low with peak heights of around 18 km alti-
 453 tude. Figure 7b depicts the smoke evolution for an injection height of 12.5 km with 2.0%
 454 BC fraction. It is clear that the peak heights for this experiment are too high with val-
 455 ues up to nearly 30 km altitude that stay elevated above 20 km altitude for several months.
 456 The e-decay timescale produced from this experiment is 6.3 months, which is too long
 457 relative to observations. Finally, Fig. 7c shows results for an injection height of 12.5 km
 458 only with 0.75% BC fraction. The plume height is more similar to observations than the
 459 other two sensitivity tests with values near 22 - 25 km altitude initially and then a steady
 460 value of ~ 18 km that lasts several months. The e-decay timescale for this experiment
 461 is 5.1 months, which is also very similar to observations.

Table 1: Smoke plume and resolution settings for different model experiments. Note that the mass column refers to the injected stratospheric mass only. The “N” in “7kmN” refers to nonhydrostatic dynamics while all other grid spacings are run with hydrostatic.

Experiment	Injection Height	Mass	BC Fraction	Model Grid Spacing
Control	13.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	2.0°/1.0°/0.25°/7km/7kmN
Perturb1	11.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	0.25°
Perturb2	12.5 km	0.2 Tg	2%	0.25°
Perturb3	12.5 km	0.2 Tg	0.5%/0.75%	0.25°

462 Given that the best estimate for the observed injection height is ~ 12 km and the
 463 model vertical resolution is only ~ 1 km near the tropopause, we assess that the opti-
 464 mal BC fraction is $\sim 1\%$. This assessment is based on the simulation with a 12.5 km in-
 465 jection height and 0.75% BC fraction, which best matched observations. The optimal
 466 BC mass fraction of $\sim 1\%$ is a 50% reduction from the control experiment as well as prior
 467 studies (e.g., Yu et al., 2019) and requires a numerically converged solution of $\sim 0.25^\circ$
 468 grid spacing. The final optimal smoke plume characteristics for the BC17 event deter-
 469 mined from GEOS simulations are as follows: 0.2 Tg stratospheric smoke mass, 1% BC
 470 mass fraction, 300 - 350 nm particle radius and ~ 12 km injection height. Table 2 lists
 471 the model resolution and optimal smoke plume characteristics determined from various
 472 studies of the BC17 event. This table serves as a quick reference for comparing the es-
 473 sential components of these studies and where the current study fits into the literature.

474 Lastly, all the simulations in this paper utilize externally mixed BC and observa-
 475 tions suggest they are internally mixed (e.g., coated by OC). Coated particles have a spe-
 476 cific light absorption mass cross section about two times larger than uncoated particles.
 477 Thus, internal mixing would need an even lower BC mass fraction in the optimal sim-
 478 ulation to match the observed stratospheric lifetime and peak height (Lee et al., 2022).

Table 2: Model resolution and optimal settings for smoke plume characteristics for BC17 simulations determined from various papers. “Y19” is Yu et al. (2019), “C19” is Christian et al. (2019), “T20” is Torres et al. (2020), “D21” is Das et al. (2021), “D22” is D’Angelo et al. (2022) and “G22” is the current study. The mass column refers to the smoke mass placed at the injection height. All studies use a coupled model (between aerosols, radiation and dynamics) except that of “C19”.

Study	Model Grid Spacing	Injection Height	BC Fraction	Mass
Y19	1.9° x 2.5°	12 - 13 km	2%	0.3 Tg
C19	2.0° x 2.5°	13.7 km	6%	0.2 Tg
T20/D21	0.5°	10 - 12 km	2.5%	0.3 Tg
D22	1.0°, 1.9° x 2.5°	13.5 km	2%	0.2 Tg
G22	0.25°	12 km	1%	0.2 Tg

479 4 Vorticity Dynamics

480 Previous studies have documented the occurrence of long-lived, anti-cyclonic vor-
 481 tices associated with wildfire smoke plumes as they rise into the stratosphere and travel

482 across the globe (Khaykin et al., 2020; Kablick et al., 2020; Lestrelin et al., 2021). The
 483 collocation of smoke plumes with a vorticity anomaly can enhance the concentration of
 484 smoke, which can lead to greater radiative absorption, self-lofting and longer stratospheric
 485 residence times. In this section, the vorticity dynamics of the smoke plumes in the GEOS
 486 simulations are analyzed to understand how these anomalies are initially formed and main-
 487 tained.

488 While previous studies have relied on potential vorticity (PV) to study these fea-
 489 tures, we focus on the vorticity field for a couple of reasons. First, one of the primary
 490 motivations for analyzing PV is to track flow features through the PV conservation prin-
 491 ciple, which is only valid for frictionless, adiabatic motions. The smoke plumes, however,
 492 do not satisfy adiabatic motions due to significant radiative effects, especially during the
 493 early stages of the plume evolution. Thus, the conservation principle does not apply and
 494 other fields, such as the total smoke mixing ratio can be used to track the plumes. Sec-
 495 ond, the PV field does provide a more concise framework for interpreting the interplay
 496 between the dynamics and heating, which is useful. However, our goal here is to under-
 497 stand how the plume vortices are formed and maintained from fundamental variables and
 498 processes predicted or diagnosed from the numerical model, such as velocities and di-
 499 abatic heating. The vorticity equation contains specific terms that allow for this type
 500 of attribution. The relative vorticity evolution equation in isobaric coordinates can be
 501 expressed as

$$502 \quad \frac{D\zeta_p}{Dt} = -(\zeta_p + f) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{2\Omega \cos \phi}{a} v + \left(\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u}{\partial p} - \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v}{\partial p} \right) + \mathbf{D}, \quad (4)$$

503

504 where ζ_p is the relative vertical vorticity on a surface of constant pressure, f is the Cori-
 505 olis parameter, Ω is the angular frequency of the Earth, ϕ is the latitude, a is the radius
 506 of the Earth and ω is the vertical velocity in pressure coordinates ($\omega = Dp/Dt$). Fol-
 507 lowing a parcel, the evolution of relative vorticity is controlled by the divergence of pre-
 508 existing absolute vorticity (first term on the right-hand-side (RHS) of Eq. 4), the merid-
 509 ional change in Earth’s rotation (beta term; second term on the RHS) and the tilting
 510 of horizontal components of vorticity into the vertical by variations in the vertical ve-
 511 locity (third term on the RHS). Finally, the \mathbf{D} term represents sub-grid scale dissipa-
 512 tion effects present in the model, which we assume to be small at the vertical levels an-
 513alyzed here. This term is still useful to include in Eq. 4 for discussion purposes.

514 Figure 8 shows vertically averaged, horizontal cross sections of relative vorticity within
 515 the smoke plumes at 6.2 days into the simulations with various grid spacings. Vortic-
 516 ity in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg) is av-
 517 eraged above 150 hPa to produce these plots. Each panel in Fig. 8 is approximately cen-
 518 tered on the peak value of the total smoke mixing ratio to highlight the center of mass
 519 of the plumes. An anti-cyclonic vortex is present in the core of the plumes for each sim-
 520 ulation as shown by the concentrated regions of negative vorticity. The peak values are
 521 around $-3.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations $\sim -7.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the 0.25° sim-
 522 ulation and $\sim -5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the 7 km simulation. The vortex is significantly more
 523 diffuse and spread out in the 2.0° and 1.0° simulations as compared to the 0.25° and 7
 524 km runs despite the fact that all simulations start with the same areal coverage of smoke.
 525 Figures 8c and 8d show that more positive vorticity begins to form and becomes entrained
 526 into the primary anti-cyclonic vortex in the higher resolution simulations. This is tied
 527 into the horizontal convergence and associated vertical transport, which is well resolved
 528 in the 0.25° and 7 km simulations as described in section 3.2.

529 At longer time periods into the simulations, the location and structure of the vor-
 530 tex is substantially different in each simulation. Figure 9 shows the same kind of plots
 531 as in Fig. 8, only at 41.2 days into the simulations. In the 2.0° run, the maximum in to-

Figure 8: Vertically averaged, horizontal cross sections of vorticity in s^{-1} contained within the smoke plumes at 6.2 days into the simulations for grid spacings at (a) 2.0° (b) 1.0° (c) 0.25° and (d) 7 km. Vorticity in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg) is averaged above 150 hPa to produce these plots.

532 tal smoke mixing ratio is very small (not shown) and the anti-cyclonic vortex has dis-
 533 appeared leaving a region of positive vorticity, which is likely the result of other synop-
 534 tic scale features. In the 1.0° case, an anti-cyclonic vortex is still present at this time,
 535 but it is very weak and diffuse with peak values around $-1.25 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ located over Ire-
 536 land and the United Kingdom. The 0.25° simulation is still maintaining a coherent vortex
 537 located to the North of Alaska with peak values a bit larger than $-2.5 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$. The
 538 main reason for the differences in location of the plumes is the height they attain, which
 539 results in transport differences from the environmental flows. The structure of the vortex
 540 and the ability to confine the smoke and assist in self-lofting is part of this process.
 541 In the 7 km simulation, the vortex is centered over Vancouver Island with similar peak
 542 values of vorticity as the 0.25° case. However, the 7 km run has much more small-scale
 543 variability in the vorticity field with many filaments of positive vorticity present in the
 544 core of the vortex, which could potentially weaken the integrated circulation through Stokes'
 545 theorem.

546 To understand how the anti-cyclonic vortex described above is formed, high fre-
 547 quency output from the 0.25° optimal simulation discussed in Section 3.3 is analyzed.
 548 Figure 10 depicts the background relative and absolute vorticity on August 12, 2017 at

Figure 9: The same type of plot as in Fig. 8, only at 41.2 days into the simulations following the smoke plume.

1800 UTC in the region where the smoke plume is initialized and 1 h before the smoke injection begins. The plots in Fig. 10 are horizontal cross sections at 150 hPa, which is at or just above the injection height of 12.5 km. The relative vorticity in Fig. 10a shows a broad region of anti-cyclonic vorticity in the smoke plume area denoted on the figure. This region of anti-cyclonic relative vorticity is also present at 100 hPa (not shown), but some bands of cyclonic relative vorticity are present as well. The absolute vorticity in Fig. 10b is positive everywhere, including at higher altitudes, which indicates that the planetary vorticity dominates over the relative vorticity. At these high latitudes, the Coriolis parameter has values over $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which easily outweighs the relative vorticity in the stratosphere.

Figure 11 shows the divergence, tilting and material tendency terms from Eq. 4 along with the relative vorticity and divergence all located within the smoke plume at 0000 UTC August 13, which is the end of the 5 h smoke forcing period. These fields are shown at 150 hPa like those in Fig. 10. The beta term in Eq. 4 is about an order of magnitude smaller than the other terms and can be neglected. The first thing to note is that the smoke forcing quickly develops an anti-cyclonic relative vorticity anomaly (Fig. 11a) within the smoke plume with peak values of $\sim -7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is about a factor of three larger than the background values shown in Fig. 10a. Collocated with this relative vorticity anomaly is a positive divergence signature (Fig. 11b) indicating the air is

Figure 10: Horizontal cross sections of vorticity in s^{-1} on August 12, 2017 at 1800 UTC in the region where the smoke plume is initialized in the model. Panels (a) and (b) show relative vorticity and absolute vorticity, respectively, both at 150 hPa. The black box denotes the approximate region where the smoke plume is injected into the model. Note the slightly larger colorbar range in panel (b) compared to panel (a), which allows better visibility

568 spreading out at this level. The 150 hPa level is near the top of the smoke plume and
 569 there is also an updraft present at this height (not shown), which is consistent with di-
 570 verging air at the top of the rising plume. Given that the absolute vorticity is positive
 571 everywhere (Fig. 10b), the diverging air is inducing a spin-down effect of the cyclonic
 572 absolute vorticity, which results in a negative divergence tendency (Fig. 11c). The di-
 573 vergence tendency values are much larger than those from the tilting tendency (Fig. 10d)
 574 at this time, so that the material tendency (Fig. 11e) is almost fully described by the
 575 divergence term. This material tendency increments the prior relative vorticity approx-
 576 imated by that shown in Fig. 10a to produce the current relative vorticity (Fig. 11a),
 577 which has a very similar structure to the material and divergence tendency terms.

578 Following the smoke plume in a Lagrangian frame of reference, Fig. 12 shows the
 579 same fields as in Fig. 11 only at 0000 UTC August 14, one day later. The fields are also
 580 shown at 150 hPa because this is where the peak smoke concentrations are located at
 581 this time. The smoke plume has grown significantly in size compared to the previous day
 582 and the relative vorticity field (Fig. 12a) shows a large region of anti-cyclonic vorticity
 583 with peak values concentrated in the plume core at or just above $-1 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. These
 584 values and those from other time periods show that the smoke plume vortex has a Rossby
 585 number ≤ 1 . In the center of the plume, there is a strip of very low vorticity that sep-
 586 arates the core of strong anti-cyclonic vorticity. This region is generally consistent with
 587 converging air (negative values of divergence in Fig. 12b), which acts to stretch the cy-
 588 clonic absolute vorticity leading to a positive divergence tendency (Fig. 12c). Outside
 589 of this core region, diverging air (positive values of divergence in Fig. 12b) is leading to
 590 a negative divergence tendency (Fig. 12c) similar to that described above at 0000 UTC
 591 August 13. The divergence tendency continues to dominate over the tilting tendency (Fig.
 592 12d) with the exception of a region on the western edge of the plume where the shear
 593 in the horizontal and vertical wind is largest. The material tendency shown in Fig. 12e
 594 reflects the divergence tendency very closely and the positive values in the center of the
 595 plume are responsible for the strip of very low vorticity observed in Fig. 12a. Smoke is
 596 present at higher altitudes (100 hPa) at this time period and the relative vorticity field
 597 at this level is compact and more uniform with positive divergence everywhere (not shown).

Figure 11: Horizontal cross sections at 150 hPa showing different fields relevant to the budget of relative vorticity within the smoke plume on August 13, 2017 at 0000 UTC. The fields are shown in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg). Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence tendency (s^{-2}), tilting tendency (s^{-2}) and the material tendency (s^{-2}), respectively.

598 This configuration is very similar to that shown in Fig. 11, which is also located at the
 599 top of the smoke plume.

Figure 12: The same as in Fig. 11 only on August 14, 2017 at 0000 UTC. Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence tendency (s^{-2}), tilting tendency (s^{-2}) and the material tendency (s^{-2}), respectively.

600 A Lagrangian conceptual model for the formation of smoke plume anti-cyclonic vortices
 601 emerges from these vorticity budget analyses. As the smoke plume absorbs solar
 602 radiation and begins to rise, the air diverges at the leading edge of the updraft, which
 603 induces a dilution of the cyclonic absolute vorticity (controlled by the sign of the Cori-
 604 olis parameter). This dilution is a strong spin-down effect of the relative vorticity field,
 605 which dominates over all other terms, producing an anti-cyclonic vortex collocated with

606 the smoke. The largest concentrations of smoke are present at these upper portions of
 607 the updraft. At levels below the leading edge, a combination of diverging and converg-
 608 ing air associated with variability of the updraft is present that can perturb the struc-
 609 ture of the vortex, but the anti-cyclonic tendency appears to be prominent.

610 Continuing to follow the smoke plume, Fig. 13 shows fields relevant to the vorticity
 611 budget at 0000 UTC September 3, which is ~ 21 days after the smoke forcing. At
 612 this time period, the plume has reached equilibrium and ceased rising, as observed by
 613 the line tracing the center of mass in Fig. 7c. The height of the peak smoke mass is 20
 614 hPa or ~ 26 km, which is the level shown for the fields displayed in Fig. 13. The anti-
 615 cyclonic vortex is still compact and strong at this time period with peak relative vorticity
 616 values of $\sim -1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in Fig. 13a. The divergence field (Fig. 13b) is weaker at
 617 this time period as the updraft has diminished and the plume has reached its peak height.
 618 Much of the divergence field in the plume is negative with a scattering of some positive
 619 regions, but when averaged over the plume, converging air is found. The dominance of
 620 converging air is more prominent at the top of the plume (10 hPa; not shown), which
 621 is consistent with a decaying updraft transitioning to a downdraft. The divergence ten-
 622 dency in Fig. 13c is dominated by positive values, which are driven by the concentra-
 623 tion of cyclonic absolute vorticity from the converging air. The tilting tendency is negli-
 624 gible at this time period so the material tendency in Fig. 13d is fully described by the
 625 divergence effect, which is acting to destroy the anti-cyclonic vortex. This process is ba-
 626 sically the exact opposite to how the anti-cyclonic vortex was formed as outlined above.
 627 Eventually, the vortex succumbs to this decay mechanism in addition to that from sub-
 628 grid scale dissipation processes as defined by the D term in Eq. 4.

Figure 13: Horizontal cross sections at 20 hPa showing different fields relevant to the budget of relative vorticity within the smoke plume on September 3, 2017 at 0000 UTC. The fields are shown in regions of total smoke mixing ratio greater than 10^{-9} kg/kg (or 1.0 kg/Tg). Panels (a), (b), (c) and (d) show relative vorticity (s^{-1}), divergence (s^{-1}), divergence tendency (s^{-2}), and the material tendency (s^{-2}), respectively.

5 Summary and Conclusions

In this paper, the dynamics of wildfire smoke plumes and their dependence on specified smoke characteristics are examined in global climate simulations at a wide range of horizontal grid spacings (2.0° , 1.0° , 0.25° , 7 km and 7 km-nonhydrostatic). While the focus of the study is on the “megafire” event that occurred in British Columbia in August of 2017, the results and discussion are relevant to a much wider range of cases. The main goal of this work is to understand how the resolved energetics of the modeling system can affect the plume dynamics and retrieval of important plume properties such as the total smoke mass and BC fraction, which together determine the BC mass, as well as the height used to initialize the plume in climate models. Significant uncertainty is present in estimating these properties, which are determined either by analyzing satellite data (e.g., (Peterson et al., 2018)), which have several impactful assumptions, or by combining climate models with satellite data (e.g., (Yu et al., 2019)). Climate models are a powerful resource, but they have their own set of uncertainties, such as the treatment of the microphysical and optical properties of smoke particles, initial conditions and resolution limitations.

Many modeling studies are conducted with very coarse grid spacing (e.g., 1° , 2° and larger) with the smoke plume injected at one or maybe a few model grid points. Simulations of this type are shown here to be very dissipative, relative to a reference simulation at 7 km, in terms of horizontal kinetic energy spectra, stratospheric lifetime, peak plume height and vorticity characteristics. For example, the 2.0° simulation that initializes the smoke plume at one grid point underestimates the stratospheric lifetime by $\sim 50\%$, peak plume height by $\sim 40\%$ and is missing a large chunk of kinetic energy and anti-cyclonic vorticity associated with the plume. In the 1.0° simulation that samples the plume with four grid points, the stratospheric lifetime and peak height are underestimated by $\sim 15\%$ and 23% , respectively, with substantial kinetic energy missing and an anti-cyclonic vortex that is very weak and diffuse at longer time periods. The 0.25° simulation (64 grid points covering plume) produced only small errors in the lifetime ($\sim 4\%$) and peak height ($\sim 6\%$), which is consistent with well-resolved kinetic energy near the plume scale and a robust vortex. These results indicate that the 0.25° simulation has essentially reached convergence. As a result, in order to produce a dynamically accurate and well-resolved simulation, the smoke plume must be sampled by the model grid at $\sim 7 - 8 \Delta x$. This “effective resolution” applies to the GEOS model studied here, but other global modeling systems produce similar results (e.g., (Skamarock et al., 2014)). A 7 km nonhydrostatic simulation was also conducted and compared to the 7 km hydrostatic experiment to examine the effects of the vertical inertial terms (and sub-grid diffusion) on the smoke stratospheric lifetime. The nonhydrostatic results show a slightly reduced stratospheric lifetime relative to the hydrostatic simulation, indicating that nonhydrostatic dynamics produces an overall dissipative effect on the plume vertical transport.

Given the above results, sensitivity tests were conducted with 0.25° spacing simulations to determine the optimal injection height of the plume and BC mass fraction using the stratospheric lifetime (~ 5 months) and to some extent peak heights (~ 22 km) (Peterson et al., 2018; Khaykin et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019; Das et al., 2021) as the truth anchor points. These tests indicate that the optimal injection height and BC mass fraction is ~ 12 km and $\sim 1\%$, respectively, assuming an external mixture. If the BC is coated or internally mixed, as suggested by field data (Lee et al., 2022), an even lower BC mass fraction will be needed to match the observed lifetime. The ~ 12 km injection height is supported by satellite observations (Peterson et al., 2018) and previous modeling studies (Yu et al., 2019). The 1% BC mass fraction is a reduction of 50% from nominal values and is based on a nearly converged model solution that matches kinetic energy spectra from theory/observations and a 7 km reference simulation. Utilizing the same injection height, under-resolved simulations at 1.0° or 2.0° grid spacing would require a large

681 and likely artificial increase in the BC fraction/mass to produce the same stratospheric
682 lifetime as the well-resolved 0.25° simulation.

683 The vorticity dynamics of the smoke plumes is also analyzed to understand the mech-
684 anisms responsible for the formation and evolution of previously documented anti-cyclonic
685 vortices (Khaykin et al., 2020; Kablick et al., 2020; Lestrelin et al., 2021), which are shown
686 here to have peak values of relative, vertical vorticity around $-2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. To provide
687 this understanding a relative, vertical vorticity budget in a Lagrangian frame of refer-
688 ence, moving with the smoke plume center of mass, was conducted. The results show that
689 the formation and evolution of the anti-cyclonic vortex is dominated by the divergence
690 tendency with only a small contribution from the tilting tendency. Further analysis pro-
691 vides the following conceptual model for the formation and destruction of smoke plume
692 anti-cyclonic vortices. As the plume rises from radiative heating, the air diverges at the
693 top of the updraft where the largest concentrations of smoke are found. This divergence
694 aloft induces a dilution of the background cyclonic absolute vorticity, which is dominated
695 by the Coriolis parameter. This dilution is a strong spin-down or negative tendency on
696 the relative vorticity field, which produces an anti-cyclonic vortex very quickly (5 h) af-
697 ter the initial injection of smoke. At later times into the simulation (~ 21 days) when
698 the plume has reached an equilibrium height, the updraft has decayed and the air is largely
699 converging aloft, which induces a concentration of the absolute vorticity field and a posi-
700 tive relative vorticity tendency that acts to destroy the anti-cyclonic vortex.

701 As described above, there are various sources of uncertainty that cloud the study
702 of wildfire smoke plumes and their climate effects. The results described in this paper
703 help to minimize the uncertainty stemming from the resolved energetics of the model-
704 ing system and illustrates how an under-resolved model configuration can affect the dy-
705 namics of the smoke plumes and the estimation of important plume properties.

706 Acknowledgments

707 Author Guimond thanks members of the NASA/GSFC Global Modeling and Assimi-
708 lation Office (GMAO), especially Matt Thompson and Michael Manyin, for providing
709 software support and answering questions on the GEOS modeling system. Discussions
710 with Gennaro D’Angelo of the Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) is acknowledged.
711 This work was funded by the LANL Laboratory Directed Research and Development (LDRD)
712 program.

713 6 Data Availability Statement

714 The GEOS model code is available at <https://github.com/GEOS-ESM/GEOSgcm>.
715 An overview of the GEOS modeling system, documentation and publications can be found
716 at https://gmao.gsfc.nasa.gov/GEOS_systems/. The datasets needed to reproduce
717 the core results of this paper can be found at the following link: [https://doi.org/10](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139799)
718 [.5281/zenodo.7139799](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139799)

719 References

- 720 Chin, M., Ginoux, P., Kinne, S., Torres, O., Holben, B. N., Duncan, B. N., . . .
721 Nakajima, T. (2002). Tropospheric aerosol optical thickness from the go-
722 cart model and comparisons with satellite and sun photometer measurements.
723 *J. Atmos. Sci.*, *59*, 461–483.
- 724 Christian, K., Wang, J., Ge, C., Peterson, D., Hyer, E., Yorks, J., & McGill, M.
725 (2019). Radiative forcing and stratospheric warming of pyrocumulonimbus
726 smoke aerosols: First modeling results with multisensor (epic, calipso, and
727 cats) views from space. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *46*(16), 10061–10071.

- Retrieved from <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1029/2019GL082360> doi: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL082360>
- 728
729
730 D'Angelo, G., Guimond, S., Reisner, J., Peterson, D., & Dubey, M. (2022). Con-
731 trasting stratospheric smoke mass and lifetime from 2017 canadian and
732 2019/2020 australian megafires: Global simulations and satellite obser-
733 vations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *127*, 1-20. doi:
734 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JD036249>
- 735 Das, S., Colarco, P. R., Oman, L. D., Taha, G., & Torres, O. (2021). The long-
736 term transport and radiative impacts of the 2017 british columbia pyrocu-
737 mulonimbus smoke aerosols in the stratosphere. *Atmospheric Chemistry and*
738 *Physics*, *21*(15), 12069–12090. Retrieved from [https://acp.copernicus.org/](https://acp.copernicus.org/articles/21/12069/2021/)
739 [articles/21/12069/2021/](https://acp.copernicus.org/articles/21/12069/2021/) doi: 10.5194/acp-21-12069-2021
- 740 Fromm, M. D., Bevilacqua, R., Servranckx, R., Rosen, J., Thayer, J. P., Herman,
741 J., & Larko, D. (2005, April). Pyro-cumulonimbus injection of smoke to the
742 stratosphere: Observations and impact of a super blowup in northwestern
743 Canada on 3-4 August 1998. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*,
744 *110*(D8), D08205. doi: 10.1029/2004JD005350
- 745 Jolly, W. M., Cochrane, M. A., Freeborn, P. H., Holden, Z. A., Brown, T. J.,
746 Williamson, G. J., & Bowman, D. M. J. S. (2015). Climate-induced varia-
747 tions in global wildfire danger from 1979 to 2013. *Nature Communications*,
748 *6*(1), 7537. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8537> doi:
749 10.1038/ncomms8537
- 750 Kablick, G. P., Allen, D. R., Fromm, M. D., & Nedoluha, G. E. (2020, July). Aus-
751 tralian PyroCb Smoke Generates Synoptic-Scale Stratospheric Anticyclones.
752 *Geophysical Research Letters*, *47*(13), e88101. doi: 10.1029/2020GL088101
- 753 Khaykin, S., Legras, B., Bucci, S., Sellitto, P., Isaksen, L., Tencé, F., ... Godin-
754 Beekmann, S. (2020). The 2019/20 australian wildfires generated a per-
755 sistent smoke-charged vortex rising up to 35 km altitude. *Communications*
756 *Earth & Environment*, *1*(1), 22. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1038/](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-020-00022-5)
757 [s43247-020-00022-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-020-00022-5) doi: 10.1038/s43247-020-00022-5
- 758 Khaykin, S. M., Godin-Beekmann, S., Hauchecorne, A., Pelon, J., Ravetta,
759 F., & Keckhut, P. (2018). Stratospheric smoke with unprecedent-
760 edly high backscatter observed by lidars above southern france. *Geo-*
761 *physical Research Letters*, *45*(3), 1639-1646. Retrieved from [https://](https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2017GL076763)
762 agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2017GL076763 doi:
763 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL076763>
- 764 Lee, J. E., Gorkowski, K., Meyer, A. G., Benedict, K. B., Aiken, A. C., & Dubey,
765 M. K. (2022). Wildfire smoke demonstrates significant and predictable black
766 carbon light absorption enhancements. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *49*(14).
767 doi: 10.1029/2022GL099334
- 768 Lestrelin, H., Legras, B., Podglajen, A., & Salihoglu, M. (2021). Smoke-
769 charged vortices in the stratosphere generated by wildfires and their be-
770 haviour in both hemispheres: comparing australia 2020 to canada 2017.
771 *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, *21*(9), 7113–7134. Retrieved from
772 <https://acp.copernicus.org/articles/21/7113/2021/> doi: 10.5194/
773 acp-21-7113-2021
- 774 Lin, S. (2004). A "vertically-lagrangian" finite-volume dynamical core for global at-
775 mospheric models. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, *132*, 2293–2307.
- 776 Malone, R. C., Auer, L. H., Glatzmaier, G. A., Wood, M. C., & Toon, O. B. (1985,
777 October). Influence of Solar Heating and Precipitation Scavenging on the Sim-
778 ulated Lifetime of Post-Nuclear War Smoke. *Science*, *230*(4723), 317-319. doi:
779 10.1126/science.230.4723.317
- 780 Molod, A., Takacs, L., Suarez, M., & Bacmeister, J. (2015). Development of the
781 geos-5 atmospheric general circulation model: Evolution from merra to merra2.
782 *Geosci. Model Dev.*, *8*, 1339–1356.

- 783 Nastrom, G., & Gage, K. (1985). A climatology of atmospheric wavenumber spectra
784 of wind and temperature observed by commercial aircraft. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, *42*,
785 950–960.
- 786 Peterson, D. A., Campbell, J. R., Hyer, E. J., Fromm, M. D., Kablick, G. P.,
787 Cossuth, J. H., & DeLand, M. T. (2018). Wildfire-driven thunderstorms
788 cause a volcano-like stratospheric injection of smoke. *npj Climate and At-*
789 *mospheric Science*, *1*(1), 30. Retrieved from [https://doi.org/10.1038/
790 s41612-018-0039-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-018-0039-3) doi: 10.1038/s41612-018-0039-3
- 791 Peterson, D. A., Fromm, M. D., McRae, R. H. D., Campbell, J. R., Hyer, E. J.,
792 Taha, G., ... DeLand, M. T. (2021). Australia’s black summer pyrocumu-
793 lonimbus super outbreak reveals potential for increasingly extreme strato-
794 spheric smoke events. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, *4*(1), 38.
795 Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-021-00192-9> doi:
796 10.1038/s41612-021-00192-9
- 797 Rienecker, M. M., Suarez, M. J., Todling, R., Bacmeister, J., Takacs, L., Liu, H.-C.,
798 ... Nielsen, J. (2008). *The geos-5 data assimilation system - documentation*
799 *of versions 5.0.1, 5.1.0, and 5.2.0* (Tech. Rep. No. 27). Greenbelt, MD, USA:
800 NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.
- 801 Skamarock, W., Park, S.-H., Klemp, J. B., & Snyder, C. (2014). Atmospheric ki-
802 netic energy spectra from global high-resolution nonhydrostatic simulations. *J.*
803 *Atmos. Sci.*, *71*, 4369–4381.
- 804 Torres, O., Bhartia, P. K., Taha, G., Jethva, H., Das, S., Colarco, P., ... Ahn, C.
805 (2020, May). Stratospheric Injection of Massive Smoke Plume From Canadian
806 Boreal Fires in 2017 as Seen by DSCOVR-EPIC, CALIOP, and OMPS-LP Ob-
807 servations. *Journal of Geophysical Research (Atmospheres)*, *125*(10), e32579.
808 doi: 10.1029/2020JD032579
- 809 Wang, J., Park, S., Zeng, J., Ge, C., Yang, K., Carn, S., ... Omar, A. H. (2013,
810 February). Modeling of 2008 Kasatochi volcanic sulfate direct radiative forcing:
811 assimilation of OMI SO₂ plume height data and comparison with MODIS and
812 CALIOP observations. *Atmospheric Chemistry & Physics*, *13*(4), 1895–1912.
813 doi: 10.5194/acp-13-1895-2013
- 814 Weisman, M. L., Skamarock, W. C., & Klemp, J. B. (1997). The resolution depen-
815 dence of explicitly modeled convective systems. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, *125*, 527.
- 816 Wikipedia contributors. (2022). *Megafire* — *Wikipedia, the free encyclope-*
817 *dia*. Retrieved from [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=
818 Megafire&oldid=1086807350](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Megafire&oldid=1086807350) ([Online; accessed 13-June-2022])
- 819 Yu, P., Toon, O. B., Bardeen, C. G., Zhu, Y., Rosenlof, K. H., Portmann, R. W.,
820 ... Robock, A. (2019). Black carbon lofts wildfire smoke high into the strato-
821 sphere to form a persistent plume. *Science*, *365*(6453), 587–590. Retrieved
822 from <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/365/6453/587> doi:
823 10.1126/science.aax1748